

A comparative study on antibacterial screening of synthesized silver nanoparticles using *Carica papaya* Linn. Leaves (Papaya) and *Morinda citrifolia* Linn. Leaves (Noni) extracts

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Abstract: Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles is an important branch in nanotechnology and it plays a vital role in material science. This research reveals preliminary photochemical investigation, green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using aqueous extracts of *Carica papaya* and *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) leaves with silver nitrate solution and also antibacterial studies for the synthesized silver nanoparticles. UV-VIS, FTIR, SEM and XRD were characterized to confirm the synthesized silver nanoparticles. The SEM analysis was employed to show that agglomerates of small grains for papaya silver nanoparticles and spherical shape for noni silver nanoparticles. The average size of synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles from XRD measurement were found to be 37.01 nm and 44.77 nm, respectively. The synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles exhibited an antibacterial activity against pathogenic bacterial strains like *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Staphylococcus* as gram positive, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E-coli* as gram negative and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Antibacterial and antifungal studies indicated that noni silver nanoparticles were found to exhibit better than papaya silver nanoparticles. The findings indicate that the synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles which can be used as a source of antimicrobes to combat multiple drug resistant to tough microorganisms.

1. Introduction

The field of nanotechnology is one of the most active researches nowadays in modern material science and technology. The most important and distinct property of nanoparticles is their exhibit larger surface area to volume ratio. The most effectively studied nanoparticles today are those made from noble metals, in particular Ag, Pt, Au, Pd.¹ The synthesis of nanoparticles and application are gaining intense importance in biomedicine, the smaller size of nanoparticles (1-100 nm) high surface area and reactively provide them the ability for therapeutic purpose in different dosage forms and dosing routes. Biological synthesis has emerged as a green alternative and these approaches have numerous advantages over chemical and

physical syntheses, because it is cost-effective, environment-friendly, and can be easily scaled up. It has great potential with environmentally benign materials such as plant extract and use of plant extracts has great advantage as they eliminate the elaborate process of maintaining cell cultures.² Among metal nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles play a significant role in the field of biology and medicine. Ag-nanoparticles have been used extensively as antibacterial agents in the health industry, food storage, textile coatings and a number of environmental applications.

An antimicrobial is a compound that kills or inhibits the growth of microbes such as bacteria. Such a compound is said to have antibacterial activity. Micro flora of a human body normally contains *B. subtilis* which is a Gram-positive, catalase-positive

and *E. coli* is a Gram-negative, facultative anaerobic, rod-shaped bacterium that is commonly found in the lower intestine of warm-blooded organisms (endotherms) and constitute about 0.1% of gut flora.³ These gut flora of humans work as a probiotic in healthy individuals which, rarely causes food poisoning.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Preparation

The Fresh leaves of papaya and noni were collected from Myeik Township, Tanintharyi Region. These were washed with water, chopped, and dried at room temperature for one week. The dried material was made powder by using grinding machine, and stored in airtight glass bottle until used of phytochemical investigation. Phytochemical examination of papaya and noni leaves aqueous extracts was determined by test tube method.

2.2 Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles

The synthesis of silver nanoparticles using papaya and noni leaves aqueous extracts were assessed by 10 mL of silver nitrate (1 mM) solution. The mixture solutions were heated on a sand bath at 60°C for 30min until change in color were observed.

The synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles were characterized by UV-VIS, FTIR, SEM and XRD analysis. The antimicrobial activity of papaya and noni silver nanoparticles were tested by agar well diffusion method. For the determination of antibacterial activity, the bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and antifungal strain such as *Candida albicans* were used and plates were incubated at 37°C overnight to know the zone of inhibition.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of *Carica papaya* and *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) leaves aqueous extracts revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, carbo- hydrates, phenolic compounds, α -aminoacids, saponins and tannins as shown in Table 1. The biomolecules found in these leaves extracts like protein and flavonoids play an important role in the reduction of Ag^+ ions.

Table 1. Results of Phytochemical Screening of Papaya and Noni Leaves Extracts.

No.	Phytoconstituents	Papaya Leave Extract	Noni Leave Extract
1	Alkaloids	+	+
2	Glycosides	+	+
3	Flavonoids	+	+
4	Carbohydrates	+	+
5	Phenolic Compounds	+	+
6	α -amino acids	+	+
7	Saponins	+	+
8	Starch	-	-
9	Tannins	+	+
10	Reducing sugar	-	-

3.2 Characterization of Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles

Reduction of silver ion into silver particle during exposure to papaya and noni leaves extracts as reducing agent could be followed by color change. As the leave extracts was mixed with an aqueous solution of silver ion complex, it was changed from yellow to dark brown in papaya silver nanoparticles and yellow to reddish brown in noni silver nanoparticles as shown in Figures 1 and 2. This is due to the excitation of the surface plasma vibrations which indicates the formation of

Figure 1. (a) Before and (b) after addition of AgNO_3 into *Carica papaya* solution.

Figure 2. (a) Before and (b) after addition of AgNO_3 into *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) solution.

Figure 3. UV- VIS spectrums of (a) papaya and (b) noni silver nanoparticles at various concentrations.

silver nanoparticles. These color change is due to the property of quantum

confinement, which is a size dependent property of nanoparticles.

UV-visible spectrum of papaya and noni silver nanoparticles had been recorded as a function of various ratio of papaya and noni leaves extracts for a fixed maturing time. The maximum absorbance of silver nanoparticle was observed in the visible range (400 nm to 500 nm). The sharp bands of synthesized silver nanoparticles were observed at 410 nm in papaya and noni silver nanoparticles which suggested that bioreduction of silver nitrate into silver nanoparticles as shown in Figure 3. The results indicated that papaya and noni leaves extract have potential to reduce silver ions into silver nanoparticles.⁴

FTIR measurements were carried out to identify the biomolecules for capping and efficient stabilization of the synthesized silver nanoparticles as shown in Table 2 and Figure 4 (a) and (b). The absorption peak at 3340 and 3356 cm^{-1} indicated -OH groups present in alcohols and phenolic groups and the peak at 1628 and 1612 cm^{-1} showed the amide bond coming from the carbonyl group of a protein. The peak found around 1380 cm^{-1} showed a stretch for C-N bonds. 1078 cm^{-1} showed a sulphonic compounds whereas the stretch for Ag-NPs were observed at $500\text{-}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Result of FTIR spectrums indicated that the carboxylic group ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$), hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$), and amine ($\text{N}-\text{H}$) groups in papaya and noni silver nanoparticles are mainly involved in the reduction of silver ions to silver nanoparticles. The FTIR spectroscopic study also confirmed that the protein present in plant leaf extracts acts as a reducing agent and stabilizer for the silver nanoparticles and prevents agglomeration. The carbonyl group of amino acid residues has a strong binding ability with metal suggesting the formation of a layer covering silver nanoparticles and acting as a stabilizing agent to prevent agglomeration in the aqueous medium. This suggests that

the biological molecules could possibly perform dual functions of formation and stabilization of silver nanoparticles in the aqueous medium.

Table 2. Band assignment for Papaya and Noni silver nanoparticles.

Observed wave number (cm ⁻¹)		Literature value (cm ⁻¹)	Band Assignment
Papaya	Noni		
3340	3356	3200-3400	Stretching vibration of OH group in alcohol and phenolic compound
1628	1612	1680-1640	C=O stretching (amide I band)
1383	1384	1315-1441	Stretching vibration of C-N in aromatic amine group
1078	1078	1054	Stretching vibration of S=O group in sulfonate
-	520	500-550	Stretching for Ag NPs

SEM analysis is employed to characterize the morphology of synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles. SEM images of papaya silver nanoparticle showed agglomerates of small grains and spherical of noni silver nanoparticle as shown Figure 5(a) and (b).

Figure 5. SEM image of silver nanoparticles using (a) papaya and (b) noni leaves extract.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. FTIR spectrum of silver nanoparticles using (a) papaya and (b) noni leaves extract.

XRD analysis was performed to determine the crystalline structure and to calculate the particle size of synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles. The prominent peaks at $2\theta = 38.074-38.061$, $44.258-44.263$, $64.401-64.346$ and $2\theta = 38.074-38.040, 44.258-44.279$, $64.401-64.221$ represents the (111), (200), (220) and planes of Bragg's reflections of the faced centered cubic structure of papaya and noni silver nanoparticles as shown in Figure 6(a) and (b). The crystalline size of papaya and noni silver nanoparticles were determined from XRD using Debye-Scherrer equation given as,

$$G = \frac{0.899\lambda}{FWHM \times \cos\theta_B} \quad (1).$$

The particle size was found to be in the range of 23-57 nm of papaya silver nanoparticles and in the range of 28-68 nm. From these data, the average particle size of synthesized papaya silver nanoparticle and noni silver nanoparticle were found to be 37.01 nm and 44.77 nm, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. XRD spectrum of silver nanoparticles using (a) papaya and (b) noni leaves extract.

3.3 Antimicrobial Activity

The antibacterial and antifungal activities of synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles tested against the following microorganism like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, as gram-positive bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* as gram-negative bacteria and *Candida albicans* as fungal strain by agar diffusion method. The results indicated that synthesized 10:9:1 ratio of papaya and noni silver nanoparticles have shown the antibacterial activities against all tested microorganism as shown in Table 3. The papaya silver nanoparticle showed maximum zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*,

(11 mm) followed by *Bacillus subtilis* (11 mm), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (11 mm), *Bacillus pumilus* (11 mm), *Escherichia coli* (11 mm) and *Candida albicans* (11 mm). The noni silver nanoparticle showed maximum zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, (15 mm) followed by *Bacillus subtilis* (15 mm), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (17 mm), *Bacillus pumilus* (14 mm), *Escherichia coli* (13 mm) and *Candida albicans* (14 mm) as shown in Figure 7. The overall observation of antimicrobial activity of synthesized silver nanoparticles indicated that the noni silver nanoparticle has more impact than the papaya silver nanoparticles. The *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) silver nanoparticle has shown the maximum against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 3. Inhibition zone (mm) of antimicrobial activity for Papaya and Noni silver nanoparticles.

	Zone of inhibition (mm)					
	Gram-positive bacteria			Gram-negative bacteria	Fungi	
AgNPs	<i>B. sub</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumils</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Candida</i>
Papaya (10:9:1)	11	11	11	11	11	11
	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Noni (10:9:1)	15	15	14	17	13	14
	(++)	(++)	(+)	(++)	(+)	(+)

4. Conclusion

Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Carica papaya* and *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) leaves extracts is a simple and eco-friendly process. The phytochemical screening of papaya and noni leaves extracts excavated the presence of various potential phytochemical constituents which interprets its medicinal values. The findings indicated that protein, phenol and

Figure 7. Inhibition zone (mm) *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) silver nanoparticles (10:9:1).

flavonoids were present in both leaves which serve as an effective reducing agent. The synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles were confirmed by the rapid colour change of plant extracts. The sharp bands of UV-VIS spectrums were observed at 410nm in synthesized papaya and noni silver nanoparticles. The FTIR spectrum shows -OH groups of alcohols, phenols band at 3340 cm^{-1} and 3356 cm^{-1} ; -NH groups of primary amine band at 1628 cm^{-1} and 1612 cm^{-1} in papaya and noni silver nanoparticles after reduction of silver nitrate into silver nanoparticles. The obtained SEM images showed agglomerates of small grains of papaya and spherical of noni silver nanoparticles. The XRD analysis showed that the average particle size of papaya and noni silver

nanoparticles were 37.01 nm and 44.77 nm respectively. The synthesized silver nanoparticles using *Carica papaya* and *Morinda citrifolia* (noni) leaves extracts exhibited an antibacterial activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus* and *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Both papaya and noni silver nanoparticles had great antibacterial activities against gram positive and gram negative bacteria but antibacterial activity of noni silver nanoparticle was more than that of papaya silver nanoparticle. In fact, the plant mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles can be used as a good therapeutic agent against human pathogens and also for the successful development of drug delivery in near future.

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References

1. Aravind, G.; Debjit B.; Duraivel, S.; Harish, G. *J. Med. Plants Stud.* **2013**, *1* (1), 7-15.
2. Niraimathi, K.L.; Sudha, V.; Lavanya, R.; Brindha, P. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* **2013**, *102*, 288–291.
3. Eckburg, P.B.; Bik, E.M.; Bernstein, C.N.; Purdom, E.; Dethlefsen, L.; Sargent, M.; Gill, S.R.; Nelson, K.E.; Relman, D.A. *Science* **2005**, *308* (5728), 1635–1638.
4. Desai R.; Venu M., S. K.; Gupta, Jha, P. K. *Nanoscience and Nano technology Letters* **2012**, *4*, 30–34.